

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF CHANGES IN POPULATION EMPLOYMENT IN RURAL AREAS OF SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract. *In this article, informal employment reduces unemployment, provides good income for the population, i.e. creates an opportunity to earn a much higher average income compared to those employed in formal jobs, increases competition in the labor market, adapts the employment market subjects to changes in the economic and institutional environment during the complex transition process.*

Keywords: *population, rural area, employment, market, labor, competition, income.*

Introduction. The market economy requires fundamental changes in ownership relations, the formation of a multi-ownership system. Accordingly, a person's role in social production and living conditions, his attitude to his work and its results, forms of assimilation of the results of the use of property will also fundamentally change. In the conditions of a market economy, a person can buy or sell the means of production and labor in the free market, fully and freely use their ownership rights. Being the owner of private property is one of the most important features of the market economy, which ensures its superiority over the planned economic system. Ownership of private property is the basis of business activity and plays a very important role in its development. In the conditions of a market economy, a person can first of all freely use his labor power, his labor capacity according to his wishes, and use it for his own purposes. becomes a worker. It is self-evident that, based on the principles of the market economy, the owner of the labor force tries to sell his commodity, that is, the labor force, at the highest possible prices in the market and to get more income from it. Whoever pays him a higher salary for each labor cost, finds that job more preferable and tries to get hired by that entrepreneur. creates a new product (service). This is reflected in the amount and quality of the work performed by the hired worker. If an entrepreneur appreciates the high labor results of a hired worker, pays a fee corresponding to the quantity and quality of his work, the hired worker is motivated materially (partly morally) to improve the labor results, and tries diligently to improve the labor indicators and his final results. Naturally, motivation from the results of such efforts and work leads to an increase in the volume and quality of produced goods and services. diligently tries to improve labor indicators and its final results. Naturally, motivation from the results of such efforts and work leads to an increase in the volume and quality of produced goods and services. diligently tries to improve labor indicators and its final results. Naturally, motivation from the results of such efforts and work leads to an increase in the volume and quality of produced goods and services.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The higher the final results of the labor of a hired worker is in full accordance with the material interests of the entrepreneur. Because the higher the labor results of the hired worker, the mass of added value absorbed by the employer, the higher his income will be. (result) is divided between both parties in certain proportions. The wage earner benefits as additional wages, and the entrepreneur benefits as additional income. As a result of this, both sides

strive for continuous improvement of labor indicators. This natural desire, along with increasing production efficiency and achieving economic growth, causes serious problems in ensuring the employment of the population.

Changes in the number of employed people in cities and villages in Samarkand region in 2017-2021

Table 1

Years	Total population, thousand people	The population of the city is one thousand people	A thousand of them are employed	Villagers, one thousand people	A thousand of them are employed	The share of the rural population in the total population, %
2017	3651.7	1372.8	266.9	2278.9	1256.1	62
2018	3720.1	1390.8	269.7	2329.3	1197.1	63
2019	3798.9	1414.7	269.4	2384.2	1186.3	63
2020	3877.4	1438.3	261.9	2439.1	1148.9	63
2021	4031.3	1483.1	279.9	2548.2	1161.3	63

In 2017, 62.4% of the region's population lived in rural areas, and in 2021, 63.2% live in rural areas. In 2017, the employment rate in rural areas was 55%, but in 2021 it decreased to 45.6%. It is these factors (intense competition in the labor market, the risk of becoming unemployed) that make wage workers employed in agriculture seek to improve their personal labor performance as much as possible in accordance with market requirements. Due to the improvement of labor results, wages of hired workers will increase, and the demand for labor force in the labor market will decrease accordingly.

A decrease in the demand for labor force in the labor market means an increase in unemployment. In fact, in the years of independence, the number of people employed in agriculture, which was flooded with artificial jobs created without reason as a result of the above-mentioned processes, has sharply decreased, and this has caused the unemployment problem in the agrarian labor market to worsen.

Changes in the level of population employment in Samarkand region in 2017-2021

Table 2

Indicators	Unit of measure	Years					2021 vs. 2017 %
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
Cocktail resources	a thousand people	2079.6	2103.4	2117.1	2125.2	2142.3	103.0
Employment rate	%	69.7	66.3	65.3	63.2	63.7	-6

The data presented in the table show that in the last five years, the labor force in Samarkand has increased by 62.7 thousand people or by 103%. The employment rate has decreased by 6%. The main reason for this is the increase in the level of informal jobs.

According to experts studying the problem of informal employment, there is an increasing trend in the share of informal employment in the economy of the employed population in all countries of the world. It is rightfully attracting the attention of the public. In this regard, the research and generalization of published scientific sources and data on the nature of informal employment, its causes, its importance in socio-economic development, the ways and possibilities of reducing it, and its prospects are different, and in many cases, the methodological ones are completely contradictory in terms of content and essence. It shows that there are approaches and theoretical views.

Based on this, reduction of informal employment as one of the conceptual directions of productive use of labor force located in the national and regional economy, especially in rural areas and currently occupying a significant place in the structure of the country's gross labor resources, in the path of socio-economic development of the country, and formal employment regulated by law an effort was made to develop scientifically based and practical suggestions and recommendations for converting to employment, raising the level of official employment. In our opinion, in order to evaluate the positive and negative aspects of informal employment, which is constantly changing in terms of its content and all dimensions in the market economy, and which today attracts the attention of many researchers, it is necessary to first of all deeply study the reasons for its origin and expansion.

The research carried out for this purpose showed that in the published literature, there are mainly two conflicting points of view in the assessment of the role of informal employment in socio-economic development, the effectiveness of the use of labor resources, and the impact on important indicators that shape the standard of living of the population. In accordance with the first point of view, informal employment is interpreted as a negative reality. In this approach, which is supported by the majority of economists and sociologists, the negative aspects of informal employment are the reduction of taxes and other payments to the state budget from employment and wages, the national legislation of the informally employed and the ILO (It is indicated that they will be deprived of the guarantees of social protection reflected in the documents of the International Labor Organization).

In accordance with the second point of view supported by a relatively small number of researchers, informal employment is evaluated as a factor that has a positive effect on the processes of social and economic development of the country. The authors of this concept consider aspects such as the positive, positive effect of informal employment: its positive effect on the level of unemployment, its role in maintaining the labor and intellectual potential of the enterprise, its importance in increasing the wages of the enterprise and personnel. A.N. Tarasova - helps to reduce unemployment and alleviate the situation in the labor market, provides an opportunity to earn income, fills low-status jobs, opens wide opportunities for efficient use of labor force, has a positive effect on the development of competition in the labor market." Similar facts can be found in other sources. Researcher A.A. Terekhova pointed out 3 positive aspects of informal employment in the labor market.

First, informal employment helps to reduce unemployment and alleviate the situation in the labor market.

Second, it gives the population the opportunity to earn a good income, that is, to earn a much higher average income than those in formal employment.

Thirdly, it helps to strengthen competition in the labor market. According to him, informal employment served as a means of adapting to the changes in the economic and institutional environment during the complex transition of market subjects, alleviating its unexpected strong shocks. It is for these reasons that gradually it began to take on a normal tone, everyone got used to it, and most people became indifferent to it. In short, it has become an institutional norm of labor relations accepted by all parties. Informal employment has become one of the unique means of getting out of the difficult economic situation that may arise in the society during the transition period to the market economy, ensuring social stability in the country, and reducing the level of unemployment. Informal employment can be seen as a kind of rapid mechanism of self-regulation of the labor market in the transition period. In the conditions of transitional difficulties, in the conditions where jobs are reduced and the number of unemployed is increasing, it is a good idea for a part of the population to solve the problem of employment on their own without officially addressing the state authorities: the unemployment rate will decrease, and the state's expenses will decrease (paid to the registered unemployed manuals and etc.).

Summarizing the opinions expressed in various sources showed that the following aspects are taken as a basis for the positive impact of informal employment on socio-economic development:

- increase in income of the parties due to saved payments, relative improvement of standard of living;

- saving time related to employment and dismissal, and for those who are self-employed, saving time related to formalization of their activity on a legal basis, saving expenses related to paperwork and other formalities;

- use of opportunities of family and kinship, mutual trust and cooperation in attracting resources, increasing efficiency of activity;

- a tool for social protection of wage workers and entrepreneurs (including self-employed entrepreneurs, their family members), unemployed people who are looking for work, who are unable to carry out formal activities within the framework of the current legislation and have no choice but to engage in informal employment to meet their most necessary physiological needs; achievement of high flexibility (elasticity) in the inter- and intra-industry competition of the labor force and in the transfer of personnel;

- that it is one of the factors of achieving a balance between labor supply and demand in the labor market;

- helps to strengthen the competitive environment in the labor market, goods and services market;

- the fact that the labor relations between the employer and the hired worker are not formalized in writing with an employment contract and an order, and that they are based only on verbal agreement, that the parties develop a culture of going beyond their word and keeping their promises;

- decrease in the unemployment rate in the country.

It is difficult to deny the above positive aspects of informal employment. On the contrary, in addition to them, it is possible to show the participation of the informally employed in the creation of the country's gross domestic product, the saving of the state's financial expenses for social protection of the population and support of entrepreneurship, the reduction of the obligation and responsibility for creating new jobs for the unemployed and ensuring their employment, etc. .

As with any economic event and event, there are both positive and negative aspects of informal employment, along with negative aspects, it has its positive aspects, of course. But in order to accept informal employment as a positive phenomenon and use it widely for the development of society, it is necessary to weigh all the positive and negative aspects of this form of employment in the internal circuit of the scales and to justify theoretically and practically that its positive aspects outweigh the negative aspects, that it can bring more benefits than harm to the country. We will discuss the negative and positive aspects of informal employment in detail later, and we will try to justify our attitude towards it. But in advance, we would like to draw the attention of respected readers to one thing: in assessing the importance and place of informal employment in the development of society, first of all, it should serve as the main criterion for determining the principles of social justice in the country. it will be necessary to justify theoretically and practically that it can bring more benefits than harm to the country. We will discuss the negative and positive aspects of informal employment in detail later, and we will try to justify our attitude towards it. But in advance, we would like to draw the attention of respected readers to one thing: in assessing the importance and place of informal employment in the development of society, first of all, it should serve as the main criterion for determining the principles of social justice in the country. it will be necessary to justify theoretically and practically that it can bring more benefits than harm to the country. We will discuss the negative and positive aspects of informal employment in detail later, and we will try to justify our attitude towards it. But in advance, we would like to draw the attention of respected readers to one thing: in assessing the importance and place of informal employment in the development of society, first of all, it should serve as the main criterion for determining the principles of social justice in the country. it will be necessary to justify theoretically and practically that it can bring more benefits than harm to the country. We will discuss the negative and positive aspects of informal employment in detail later, and we will try to justify our attitude towards it. But in advance, we would like to draw the attention of respected readers to one thing: in assessing the importance and place of informal employment in the development of society, first of all, it should serve as the main criterion for determining the principles of social justice in the country.

Before a detailed analysis of the scientific views of the supporters of both points of view and expressing some of our own opinions about them, it is necessary to correctly assess the role and importance of informal employment in socio-economic development, to which macroeconomic indicators and in what direction, and at the micro level, the final result of its economic activity. It should be noted that it is very important to reveal the mechanisms of influence on the results, the income of the employer and hired workers, and their mutual relations. The importance of these issues is explained by the fact that if we agree with the supporters of the first approach and consider informal employment as a negative reality, in the future, a sharp reduction in the share of informal workers in the number of employed people in the economy, we will have to find ways to eliminate it gradually. In other words, it becomes an urgent task for us to carry out a consistent fight against informal employment. The fight against informal employment should take a strong place in the structure of the economic and administrative means of the state's economy regulation. Strict administrative and economic sanctions must be imposed on all persons, employers, and hired workers who are involved in informal employment and who allow it. On the contrary, if we recognize informal employment as a positive phenomenon, that is, if we support the manifestations of the second point of view on this problem. , to further expand this employment in the future, develop it superior to other forms of employment, we will have to develop and put into practice the mechanisms of support and encouragement of persons using informal employment. The policy of the state to regulate the economy and labor relations should also be aimed at expanding the scope of informal employment and effectively supporting it in every way. In our opinion, informal employment in Samarkand creates difficulties in the process of economic reforms. Today, it is not wrong to conclude that it causes more harm than good in the development

of the region, including solving problems in the field of labor economy. However, here we should not ignore the fact that , informal employment is not an economic reality unique to the national economy of Uzbekistan, which is experiencing transitional difficulties. Informal employment, as recognized by the UN, is an economic phenomenon that is increasingly expanding throughout the countries of the world and has a great negative impact on socio-economic development. This form of employment is not only backward, but also developing and even developed countries are taking root more and more. So, It would not be correct to connect the roots of informal employment only with the difficulties of the transition period or the socio-economic situation of the country, the economic helplessness of some entrepreneurs and hired workers. Both the employer and the hired worker benefit to a certain extent from this situation, which is common in labor relations in the field of the market economy, because the costs of various payments to the state budget and the employment fund are saved. However, such relations formed in the labor market of the agrarian sector bring economic benefits to a certain extent for the entrepreneur (employer) and the employees employed in the enterprise, in return for not paying official fees and expenses, but from the point of view of society, such a situation leads to great losses and, ultimately, general inefficiency. Market relations are settled,

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